

A ROADMAP TO TEACHING LEARNING PROCESS FOR BETTER FUTURE

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Cite This Article: Dr. Inderpreet Kaur, "A Roadmap to Teaching Learning Process for Better Future", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 132-136, 2018.

Abstract:

Education is a broader concept which encompasses other domains which makes an individual distinct from the other. Teaching learning plays an important role in the process of education. Individual students may be better suited to learning in a particular way, using distinctive modes for thinking, relating and creating. The notion of students having particular learning styles has implications for teaching strategies. Because preferred modes of input and output vary from one individual to another, it is critical that teachers use a range of teaching strategies to effectively meet the needs of individual learners. If we want our students to learn innovative teaching strategies. Teachers need to know the roadmap for achieving the ultimate objective of education. This paper suggests some of the strategies for effective learning.

Key words: Education, Roadmap to Teaching Learning process

Introduction:

Education is an extremely powerful instrument for social change and imaginative teaching practice is the most efficient way to improve the quality of our education. The problems which society encounters are basically the issues of educational institutions which are required to be inventive as they instruct new aptitudes and grow new bits of knowledge and methodologies towards the solving of social problems which the country faces. Students must be enabled to have the capacity to withstand the worldwide difficulties of the 21st century. A key execution marker of any educational institution is the education quality particularly in teaching and learning areas. Teaching and learning are like an identical representation of each other. Often, the most acknowledged standard for estimating good teaching is the measure of student learning. The literature on the relationship of teaching and learning identifies three specific roles: teacher as the human relations specialist, as a facilitator and as motivator. There is reliably high relationship between students' 'ratings of the "amount learned" in the course and general appraisals of the teacher and the course.

Teachers use distinctive strategies relying upon the idea of subject, number of students, and the offices accessible in the classroom. While in separate learning process, the teacher stays in one area by providing notes and students learn lessons by remaining another helpful area as required. Owing to the web generation, students jump at the chance to interface themselves in community condition which encourages the understanding and learning. Subsequently, the teacher-oriented teaching techniques are cliché and students prefer learner-oriented teaching techniques. Numerous intelligent innovations including online or internet based learning and teaching are the one of the most significant elements of the student-centered teaching. The application of inventive teaching and learning methods is basic in the event that we are to propel and motivate learning and additional eagerness on the part of students for learning, while at colleges and in fact for lifelong learning. The part of education is to guarantee that while scholastic staffs do instruct, what is educated ought to likewise be understandable to students radiating from socially and phonetically differing foundations and that they quickly get comfortable with the normal guidelines.

It is usually the case that students underachieve due to the way that they have not got a handle on an attention to the level of evaluation or what it is that the teacher anticipates from them. Lecturers should accordingly put forth a concentrated effort to using creative strategies with the goal that the students 'learning process is as free-streaming as could be expected under the circumstances and that the procedure they receive is helpful for learning'. Creative teaching and learning techniques, for example, short lecture, simulation, pretending, portfolio development and problem-based learning (PBL) are exceptionally valuable in tending to the quick technological advances and creating work environments that will be required in the foreseeable future. As far as the social constructivist worldview, learning is not a social process which is neither one of the limited to an individual, nor is it latent, meaningful learning just occurs once an individual is occupied with social activities. This incorporate building up of the ability of students to utilize thoughts and information, testing of ideas and evidence, generation of new ideas and proof, help of self-improvement and advancement of a student's capacity to design and deal with their learning experience. Basic resources are in this way grown so that students start to ask important questions instead of just answer questions. The level of teaching effectiveness is an inquiry that diseases higher education for various decades. It

- ✓ Characterizes effective teaching as "that which produces helpful and deliberate student learning using suitable techniques" which is an angle that this paper is looking to address. What constitutes effective teaching?

- ✓ Incorporate both teaching and learning in their definition: "production of circumstances in which suitable learning happens; molding those circumstances is the thing that successful teachers have figured out how to do adequately".

However, they may even now advantage from aptitudes that are created while at an establishment, particularly the certainty they acquire from new life experiences. What is required for all students, even those that drop out, is profound instead of surface learning.

Innovative teaching is necessary for the present and future of education to help students to reach their full potential. Higher education should serve the long term intellectual needs of the student, for example, whether providing new material by teachers helped the student to gain new insights or opened up new channels of intellectual stimulation or enhanced student's essential and creative thinking power?. Innovative teaching is a necessity for all teachers in order to meet the educational needs of the new generations. However, teachers' competency for innovative teaching is a key factor influencing innovative teaching performance. Some research points out that many teachers lack competencies for innovative teaching!

Review of Literature:

There are various attributes expected of the creative teacher which incorporate modesty, valor, unprejudiced nature, liberality, compassion, eagerness, judgment and creative energy [3]. It is these teachers who will inject deeper learning in their students. [4] Refer to intelligent work on and learning and give various cases of appearance in real life by both academic staff and students. The concentration must move from 'talk and chalk' to how students learn and lecturers need to impart a profound way to deal with learning by giving students varied imaginative invigorating learning environments keeping in mind the end goal to make a deeper learning. Learning should be the aftereffect of lecturer motivation and assistance and the students 'learning-centered exercises in which they are locked in and for which they expect proprietorship (Biggs, 1999). This is the reason it is basic that all teachers genuinely take part in intelligent practice and try different things with inventive strategies where required.

There are various qualities expected of the inventive speaker which incorporate modesty, bravery, unbiasedness, liberality, sympathy, energy, judgment and creative ability [5]. It is these teachers who will imbue deeper learning in their students. [6] Allude to intelligent practice and learning and give various cases of appearance in real life by both academic staff and students. The center must move from 'talk and chalk' to how students learn and lecturers need to impart a profound way to deal with learning by giving students varied inventive empowering learning environments so as to make a more profound learning. Learning ought to be the aftereffect of speaker inspiration and assistance and the students 'learning-centered exercises in which they are locked in and for which they accept proprietorship [7]. This is the reason it is basic that all instructors truly participate in intelligent practice and try different things with creative techniques where required. They should endeavor to utilize customized methodologies to educate and effectively connect with students in course content. [8] Contends that with a specific end goal to accomplish quality teaching and learning, more prominent consideration must be paid to teaching and learning practice. Plainly conventional procedures of 'talk and chalk' which are teacher-centered are not satisfactory for current students and that effective teaching and learning is not occurring at the coveted level. Amazing learning results are achievable given that students assume more noteworthy control over their own learning. This thought is bolstered by [9] who keeps up that greater student association in self-appraisal and that of their companions is helpful to them. Students must be drenched in genuine educational modules substance and errands that are requesting and important to their lives and futures. They should endeavor to utilize customized methodologies to instruct and effectively draw in students in course content. [10] Contends that keeping in mind the end goal to accomplish quality teaching and learning, greater consideration must be paid to teaching and learning practice. Plainly customary techniques of 'talk and chalk' which are teacher-centered are not satisfactory for current students and that effective teaching and learning isn't occurring at the coveted level. High-quality learning outcomes are achievable provided the students assume more prominent control over their own learning. This thought is upheld by [8] who keeps up that more prominent student involvement in self-appraisal and that of their companions is advantageous to them. Students must be drenched in true educational programs substance and assignments that are requesting and applicable to their lives and futures.

Current Status of Teaching Learning Process:

Tragically, numerous instructors have received customary technique of teaching and learning. The teaching is predominantly in view of the syllabus and endorsed reading material. In numerous address rooms, teaching and learning techniques are obsolete and hypothetical information is still dispersed through the technique of talk and chalk. Learning is a procedure which should create wanted changes in the conduct of students. Therefore, the learning situations used in the address rooms are vital for the comprehension of the ideas educated. Learning happens but when understanding is picked up, and when the procedures are comprehended, in short when cooperation occurs between the speaker and the students and amongst students and their companions. Teachers still trust that information is exchanged with their students, however in reality students learn by doing and this is strengthened by the utilization of innovative teaching techniques. In any case,

it appears that when teachers endeavor to be inventive in the learning environment, numerous miss the mark, and students hence, regularly like to be surveyed in a customary way. Inventive strategies are along these lines apparent to be a hindrance for them. Students complain that a few appraisals don't in any capacity measure their genuine realizing and what they are surveyed with is insignificant to this present reality of work.

It is the undertaking of a speaker to facilitate learning and to rouse, support and coach students to accomplish scholastically with the utilization of inventive strategies and to by and large advance enthusiasm for their subject which ought to go past the our dividers of a teacher room. Students need adequate chance to impart thoughts to the teacher and additionally with their companions and this winds up troublesome if near unimaginable particularly with expansive gatherings of students in one class.

A Roadmap to Teaching Learning Process:

The training or application of inventive and interactive teaching techniques in educational organizations has the potential to enhance the quality of education, as well as to empower students or future age of the nation by fortifying administration and electrify the push to accomplish the human development objective for the country.

Creative Teaching:

Take the help of creative tools to stimulate creativity. Include playful games or forms of visual exercises that will excite the young minds and capture their interest. This is a time tested method to identify young student's creative abilities and encourage creative contributions. Bring aspects of creativity into all your subjects, be it mathematics, science, or history. Think of ways to develop their creative ideas. Encourage different ideas, give them freedom to explore

Real World Teaching:

Teacher should try to link the lessons to real world learning. Infusing real world experiences into your instructions will make teaching moments fresh and enrich classroom learning. Relating and demonstrating through real life situations, will make the material easy to understand and easy to learn. It will spark their interest and get the children excited and involved. You can make use of smart apps for preschoolers to make these sessions all the more interesting

Collaborative Teaching:

Everyone knows, the end result of collaborative efforts is always immense. Think about spending some quality time with your colleagues. Ask them to share their views on improving teaching methods, you can see many of them come up with interesting strategies. So, collaborate and introduce innovative teaching methods.

Role Play:

Teaching through role play is a great way to make children step out of their comfort zone and develop their interpersonal skills. This method comes in handy, especially when you are teaching literature, history or current events. The role playing approach will help the student understand how the academic material will be relevant to his everyday tasks.

Brainstorming:

Brainstorming is a large or small group activity that encourages students to focus on a topic and contribute to the free flow of ideas. By expressing ideas and listening to what others say students adjust their previous knowledge or understanding, accommodate new information and increase their levels of awareness. Students enjoy and at the same time learn effectively.

Peer Tutoring:

Peer tutoring involves pupils working in pairs in the roles of tutor and tutee. It is a method of engaging in one-to-one instruction and is effective from both an academic and social point of view. Both tutor and tutee benefit from peer tutoring, it is an efficient use of teacher time and provides active learning opportunities, something highly endorsed in the Primary Curriculum. It is an underlying principle of the curriculum that the child should be an active agent in his or her own learning

Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Lessons (POGIL):

Process Oriented Guided Inquiry Lessons are part of a learning strategy that has both a constructivist and social component. In other words, it focuses on using the real life experiences of the learner to create knowledge and considers how a student relates to the environment where they are taught. When engaging in POGIL's, the teacher assigns text to students, and then poses a set of questions that they can only answer by exploring the text that was given. In this process, the teacher has to fight the urge to give students any answers or facts to memorize. Their main role is to pose questions that provoke the students to look more deeply at the text they are given.

Reality Pedagogy:

Reality Pedagogy is an approach to teaching and learning that focuses on teachers gaining an understanding of student realities, and then using this information as the starting point for instruction. It begins with the fundamental premise that students are the experts on how to teach, and students are the experts on content. Reality pedagogues/teachers believe that, for teaching and learning to happen, there has to be an exchange of expertise between students and teacher. For this exchange to happen, teachers need a set of tools

called the “5 C’s” to gain insight into student realities, and allow students to express their true selves in the classroom. These tools are:

- ✓ Co generative dialogues: Where teachers and students discuss the classroom and both suggest ways to improve it.
- ✓ Co teaching: Where students get opportunities to learn content and then teach the class.
- ✓ Cosmopolitanism: Where students have a role in how the class operates and in what is taught.
- ✓ Context: Where the neighborhood and community of the is seen as part of the classroom.
- ✓ Content: Where the teacher has to acknowledge the limitations of his/her content knowledge and work to build his/her content expertise with students

Flipped Classroom:

One of the most popular new approaches to teaching is the flipped classroom. This approach involves a process where the typical lecture that happens in the classroom occurs at home. Students watch lectures on video, and then return to school to engage in the exercises they would traditionally have for homework, and to ask questions based on the lecture they watched on their own at home. When students watch videos at home, they can stop and go and at their own pace, and take notes their leisure. When they return to school, they can work in groups to discuss what they watched, and/or have their questions answered by the teacher. In this process, students create, collaborate and learn at their own pace, and apply what they have learned at home in the classroom

Simulation and Role-Playing:

Reenactment of situations and cross examination of case studies, involving staff and visitors in inns and different tourism operations, are helpful in critical thinking and in building up the argumentation and logical skills students that students require in the realm of-work. Such activities advance understanding and profound discovering that are the requirements for long haul knowledge acquisition. This strategy requires arranging by the teacher who must have clear goals with respect to the learning outcomes. Student preparation might be required for specific reenactments and pretending. Teacher appraisal and in addition associate and self-appraisal might be utilized to evaluate student understanding. Note that these strategies take into consideration more prominent understudy self-reflection while at the same time likewise upgrading different territories of the learning process. Speaker and companion criticism are essential in helping students to build up their problem-solving abilities and strategies.

This approach to learning is based on the idea that learners respond to stimuli in their environment. The role of the learning facilitator, therefore, is to provide relevant and useful stimuli so that the learner responds to and gains the required knowledge or experience.

Problem Based Learning:

Students are given a real-world problem then they work together to find a solution to this. In Australia, nursing programmes have begun to embrace this style of teaching and learning because it challenges the students to work as if they’re dealing with real problems they’ll encounter in the workplace. Teachers find it invaluable because students learn more with this method.

Conclusion:

Any innovative teaching and learning method isn't an easy solution or general cure. It cannot supplant a traditional teaching philosophy in instruction, rather it underpins it. In any case it is obvious from the writing, that innovative teaching strategies do provide students with more prominent involvement in managing the universe of business related issues they experience. Innovative teaching systems will prompt a learning society in which the imaginative and scholarly capacities of understudies will enable them to meet the objectives of change and advancement, where understudies claim to encounter issues with evaluation, the general contention is that the speakers have not sufficiently clarified what is expected of them. Different student problems incorporate over the top workloads and inadequate input. Instructors need to think about these perspectives while receiving any strategy. Given the constructivist idea of the PBL approach, there is a bigger maintenance of knowledge and students make the most of their learning experience much more than in customary methodologies.

Education for the future requires assortments of models and teaching strategies. We have to stay discerning of the socially and other particular needs of our students and must not think little of the impact of technology, for example, There is no Eurocentric or other outline for education which can be passed around from nation to nation, however we ideally have enough information to comprehend that an educational system in view of the impartial treatment of all students in the social blend that is an ethical need, but on the other hand is politically, socially and monetarily helpful for our nation.

References:

1. Barker, J., & Gossman, P. (2013). The Learning Impact of a Virtual.
2. Demian, P., & Morrice, J. (2012). The use of virtual learning environments and their impact on academic performance. Higher Education Academy

3. Best, John, W. & Khan James V. (2000). *Research in Education* (Seventh Ed.). New Delhi: Prentice - Hall.
4. Bhartia Ranjana, (2008). Blending Traditional Earning with Online Learning in Teacher Education, *University News*. Vol. 46 No. 04.pp.11-13.
5. Crosling G, As-Saber, Rahman N (2008). 'Postgraduate International students and Independent Learning', Paper at International Conference on Postgraduate Education, 16-17 December, Penang, Malaysia.
6. Crosling G, Edwards R, Schroder W (2008). 'Internationalizing the Curriucum. The implementation experience in a Faculty of Business and Economics', *J. Higher Edu. Policy Manag.* 30(1): 107-121.
7. Dandapani S.,(2008). Effective Teaching through Feedback, *Edutracks*. Vol. 7 No. 6.pp 15-17.
8. Hofstetter, F. T. (1995). *Multimedia Literacy*, New York: McGraw-Hill.
9. John Biggs (1999). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University*. SRHE and Open University Press, Buckingham.
10. Liu Z (2010). Thought on achieving modernization in higher education. *Chinese Higher Education*, (10), 29.
11. Murahari B., (2008). *Teaching Today for Tomorrow*, *University News*. Vol. 46 No. 15.
12. Rothwell A (2008). Think global, teach local. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 42 (4):313-323.
13. Salkind Neil J. (2006). *Encyclopedia of Human Development*. New Delhi, Sage Publications India Pvt. Ltd.
14. Stensaker B (2008). 'Outcomes of Quality Assuarance: A discussion of knowledge, methodology and valididty', *Quality in Higher Education*, 14 (1): 7-11.
15. Tapscott, D. (1998). *Growing Up Digital: The Rise of the Net Generation*, New York: McGraw-Hill
16. Zubizarreta J (2009). *The Learning Portfolio: Reflective Practice for Improving Student Learning*, Josse -Bass, San Francisco, 35-51.